

ENVIRONMENTAL PHYSICS
GROUP

NEWSLETTER

No. 12
August/September 1995

THE INSTITUTE OF PHYSICS

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Contributions

Contributions, news items or meeting notices are welcome from members and non-members alike and should be sent to:

Dr Ranjeet Sokhi	School of Environmental Sciences University of Greenwich, Deptford Campus, Rachel McMillan Building, Creek Road, London SE8 3BU Tel: (0181) 316 8000 · Fax: (0181) 316 8205
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EPG Membership

IoP/EPG membership enquiries are encouraged from both physicists and non-physicists with an interest in topics in "Environmental Physics". For further details contact:

The Membership Manager	The Institute of Physics 47 Belgrave Square, London SW1X 8QX Tel: (071) 235 6111 · Fax: (0171) 259 6002 e-mail: iop@uk.ac.ulcc
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The views expressed in this newsletter are those of the authors and not those of the Institute of Physics unless stated otherwise.

Welcome to Issue number 12.

This will be my last issue of the EPG Newsletter. Unfortunately, my professional life must come first for the moment and so I have had to resign from the EPG Committee although I still hope to be involved with EPG affairs. Ranjeet Sohki and a new member of the Committee, David Pearson, will be taking over production of the Newsletter so please address any queries or comments to Ranjeet at his address on the contents page. I would like to thank those who have contributed to the newsletter and I hope that all the EPG membership will continue to support the new Editors.

I cannot stress enough how important the Newsletter is to the EPG because it represents one of the few direct links the Committee has with the membership as a whole. I have met several members who have expressed the opinion that they couldn't justify the expense of IoP membership because they didn't get much from it. I'm afraid my only response to that was that the Committee tries to give the membership as wide a range of meetings as possible and if our membership want something different then they should enter a dialogue with either the Committee or with other EPG members and use the Newsletter as a forum for discussing ideas. Whatever the Committee can organise will only succeed with the support of the EPG membership as a whole. This is **YOUR** Group and the Committee is working on **YOUR** behalf so if your not happy about something you should say so. The Committee can not work in a vacuum.

Anyway, enough of the soap box. We have a summary of the presentation given at this years AGM on 10 May. Unfortunately, our original speaker, John Monteith, was unwell and so our Chairman, John Stewart, stepped in and presented some results of worked performed at the Institute of Hydrology at Wallingford. Some of you may remember from Congress '94 that his primary interest is in the understanding of water utilisation in semi-arid developing countries. John Monteith has already agreed to reschedule his talk and my information is that it will be one of the Plenary lectures at Congress '96. The EPG will be taking part in this event and at the moment our plans are at a very early stage but few sketchy details of the proposed programme are given in the *Future Meetings* section.

Another important feature to be mentioned is the new line-up for the EPG Committee and this is described in more detail on page 5 together with brief biographies of the new Committee members. The new blood will bring a fresh view to EPG activities but inevitably the EPG will only succeed if it is fully supported by the EPG membership as a whole. Remember, the Committee works for **YOU**, so use it.

Geoff Hassall
Newsletter Editor

The Annual Lecture: Summary

In the balance – Hydrology of the Sahel:

The contribution of Environmental Physics to solving problems in semi-arid countries

Sahelian regions occur both in the northern and southern Africa where the true desert borders the areas of plentiful rainfall. In the Sahelian regions the rainfall is extremely variable both spatially and temporally, during the year and from year to year. In the past nomadic herdsman moved to where there was sufficient water and grazing. With increasing population pressure in Africa, agriculturalists are moving in to the drier areas and experiencing increasing problems. Two particular examples show how a new understanding of the underlying physical processes involved resulting from studies performed by environmental physicists from the Institute of Hydrology have led to suggestions for possible improvements of current agricultural methods.

In Niger, millet is planted in rows 1.2 m apart so that even at maturity much of the soil is not covered by the crop. Using measurements and modelling approaches environmental physicists have shown that a third of the rainfall is directly evaporated from the bare soil and never reaches the rooting zone to be available to the crop to produce grain. Possible remedies to reduce this loss of valuable water have been suggested. Growing suitable crops between the rows could exploit this water or covering the soil with stones, to permit percolation of the rain but extend the evaporation pathway and hence reduce the loss by evaporation.

The second example of the benefits of environmental physics comes from Zimbabwe. In certain areas pumping tests showed that wells could not supply sufficient irrigation water even for small vegetable plots. However, by increasing the length of tubing in contact with the aquifer by drilling horizontal holes up to 30 m long in a number of directions at the bottom of the well could increase the yield by an order of magnitude. Besides designing these collector wells scientists at Wallingford have carried out pilot schemes to demonstrate that villages can use this water to irrigate vegetable gardens. These vegetables improve the nutritional value of the villagers' diet as well as the flavour and any excess can be sold to surrounding villages. These pilot schemes have been so successful that there is now a demand for more collector well schemes. It is expected that aid agencies will pay for the drilling, while the villages will operate the system themselves, using hand pumps.

It is increasingly appreciated that environmental physicists have to do more than just study and understand environmental systems, they have to design and demonstrate solutions using appropriate technology.

John Stewart

Chairman, EPG

Committee Changes

Several new Committee members were announced and agreed at the AGM. This included the election of three new full members and a co-opted member. This reshuffle came about as a result of several of the existing Committee members resigning over the past year. The resigning members were John Harries, Geoff Hassall and Mike Smithson. These were all due primarily to pressures of work and/or changes in job. Responsibility for the Newsletter has been handed to Ranjeet Sokhi and one of our new Committee member, David Pearson. Two other new members are John Garland and Terry Jackson and we have also been joined by Richard Clarke who will be a co-opted member of the Committee.

It is intended that this "new-blood" will give the Committee a broader base in the environmental physics community which will, in turn, help us to provide a wider range of meetings, visits and other activities through which members of the EPG can meet and exchange views. The EPG exists to raise awareness among physicists that in these changing times there are other opportunities for them to explore and that "physics" isn't just quantum mechanics and star-gazing.

To introduce some of our new Committee members here are three brief biographies. My apologies to John Garland for not including him in this issue but his information was not available at the time of going to press.

Richard Clarke is a Pollution Inspector for Her Majesty but before taking on this role he worked for 12 years for British Coal at the Environmental Branch of the Mining Research and Development Establishment. Since joining the HM Inspectorate of Pollution he has been responsible for regulating a wide range of potentially polluting industries under the Environmental Pollution Act of 1990. He also has responsibility for the holding, accumulation and disposal of radioactive materials.

Terry Jackson is a Lecturer at the Belfast Institute of Further and Higher Education and his subject is **Physics and Energy Systems**. He has an M.Sc in *Plasma Physics* and an M.Phil in *Energy Systems*. In his "spare" time he has advised various Select Committees and was appointed to the Government Advisory Panel on Energy Conservation. He has also taught Environmental Studies at the Open University.

David Pearson graduated in *Theoretical Physics* from the University of York in 1987 and went on to study at Imperial College for a Ph.D in *Plasma Physics*. Since 1992 he has been working on aspects of the surface radiation budget and later on the processing of remote sensing data at the Unit for Thematic Information Systems (NUTIS) at the University of Reading.

International Energy Agency: Energy Environment Update

An **Energy Environment Update** has been published recently by the IEA which discusses the wide range of work under way at the IEA which analyses energy-related environmental impacts and the options available to mitigate those impacts, especially in the field of greenhouse gas emissions. It is intended to be "a service to administrations, non-governmental organizations and the energy community" as a whole. In this issue two key areas are discussed:

- Climate Change Policy Initiatives in Central and Eastern Europe, and
- Energy-Related Greenhouse Gas Abatement.

The EEU is available free on request and a second issue will be published later in the year. Readers interested in further information about this work, or in the schemes and activities organised through the IEA, should contact either the Energy and Environment Division of the IEA, or the IEA Public Information Office, at the following address:

International Energy Agency (IEA)

2 rue Andre Pascal,
75775 Paris Cedex 16, France

Environmental Technology Best Practice Programme

This Programme is a joint DTI and DOE initiative managed by AEA Technology through ETSU and the National Environmental Technology Centre. It is a Government initiative offering free information and advice on environmental issues, legislation and technology. It is aimed at companies with a need for advice about their future operations with an eye on how this may impact on the environment. The Programme combines many elements of which one is an Environmental Helpline which is designed to give assistance in solving a company's environmental problems and to provide solutions specific to their needs.

Further information can be obtained from:

Environmental Technology Best Practice Programme,

ETSU, Harwell, Oxon OX11 0RA

The UK GER Office Newsletter: The Globe (Issues 24 and 25).

Since the last issue of the EPG newsletter two copies of **The Globe** have been published. Issue 24 (April, 1995) was a *Climate Change Special* and will be of interest to many of the EPG membership. It was primarily a report on the first meeting of the **Conference of the Parties (COP-1) to the Framework Convention on Climate Change (FCCC)** which took place in March/April 1995, in Berlin. In essence, this was a meet-

ing of those countries which signed the **First Framework Convention on Climate Change** in Rio. Its purpose was to review the adequacy of the Conventions commitments in combating climate change. It was also hoped that in light of this assessment that procedures could be finalised for the implementation and future working of this initiative. It was the first of an annual series of conferences which will review the operation of this convention. The result of this first meeting was "the initiation of a process which will lead to a strengthening of controls of greenhouse gases, with the aim of preparing a protocol for agreement in 1997 ..." – according to the politicians!

Issue 25 marked a change from the thematic approach used in the past and covered many more news items with short articles about **GENIE**, the **Centre for Earth Observation** (more about the CEO later in this issue), UN environmental initiatives and several pieces on "sustainable" topics, for example, the **Sustainable Biosphere Project**. You'll have to get hold of a copy of the **Globe** to find out what this all means.

Issues 26 and 27 return to a more usual format with themes dealing with "Technological and Policy instruments to mitigate adverse impacts of global change" (**Globe 26**) and an **Ozone special** with reports from the **Seventh Meeting of the Parties to the Montreal Protocol** (issue 27).

Further information and copies of **The Globe**, as well as details about other activities of the UK GER Office, contact:

The UK GER Office

Polaris House, North Star Avenue, Swindon SN2 1EU
Tel: 01793 411768/411779 ; Fax: 01793 444513

The Internet: World Wide Web

For all of our members with access to the Web here are a few more URLs which have been brought to my attention.

Global Environmental Network for Information Exchange:

GENIE <http://www-genie.lut.ac.uk/>

International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme: Data and Information System

IGBP-DIS http://xtreme.gsfc.nasa.gov/igbp1/dis_home.html

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, USA

NOAA <http://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/>

National Environmental Research Council, UK

NERC <http://www.npm.ac.uk/>

United Nations Environmental Programme

UNEP <http://www.unep.ch>

The British Atmospheric Data Centre

The BADC was mentioned in the last issue of the newsletter and just recently I have received some further information about BADC activities.

A leaflet is now available which gives a brief overview of the BADC, the facilities it offers and how to use it. They are in the process of producing a more extensive brochure which will be available "... in due course". I won't bore you with the Mission Statement; you can read that in the previous newsletter. In essence, the BADC stores a variety of data on the atmosphere which is available for dissemination to the scientific community. The amount of information is expanding all the time so specific enquiries should be directed to the Project Manager, Dr Peter Allan.

Their facilities comprise not only the data but the computer equipment used to store and process the data as well as the support staff at the Centre. All of the BADC computing facilities are accessible through JANET and the Internet. The staff are on-hand to ease access for users by answering any queries, registering new users and organising user group meetings.

Using the BADC

The BADC is used by several hundred researchers situated in UK universities and research establishments. There are three ways in which someone can gain access to data held at the BADC. They can use the World Wide Web interface, they can log in to a BADC computer via the JANET network and make use of software that is available on our computers, or they can copy files over the network from RAL to their own computer for further analysis.

The World Wide Web interface is growing in popularity, although not all of our data holdings are available through this route as yet. This is the recommended route for new users. The Web service provides general information about the BADC, information on individual datasets and links to other data centres that have Web servers. The URL¹ for the BADC is

<http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>

Some users prefer just to copy data to their own computer using the ftp interface. To do this, make an ftp connection to gdfxa.ag.rl.ac.uk. Most datasets are available by logging in with the username anonymous. However, access to certain datasets is restricted. In order to copy these datasets, you will need your own account on the computer. Before being granted access to restricted data, you must sign a form agreeing to comply with the restrictions placed on the use of the data by the owners of that data.

Finally, there is the menu interface. This is a hierarchical menu system through which a user proceeds in order to accomplish their required data processing operations. It used to be the sole interface available, but it is now being superseded by the Web and ftp. For the present, however, it remains the only way of accessing certain datasets and provides better plotting facilities for many datasets.

Also from the BADC

The CEO Experimental Demonstrator in Global Change Atmosphere

The Commission of the European Communities is currently conducting studies through the Joint Research Centre as part of setting up a Centre for Earth Observation (CEO). Despite the name, this will be a distributed system, involving existing data provision systems. The CEO is currently in the pathfinder phase and is conducting several studies to capture user requirements. One of these studies is in the area of Global Change Atmosphere. This study is being led by the Hadley Centre. Part of the study consists of setting up an Experimental Demonstrator using the World Wide Web.

The purpose of this note is to advertise the existence of the Experimental Demonstrator and to ask you to try it out and give feedback on the demonstrator. This is an opportunity for you to influence the design of the CEO.

The Experimental Demonstrator provides the following facilities:

- Access to systems to search for high level information
- Access to catalogues of meta-data
- Access to a sample dataset (TOMS)
- Access to information about a sample dataset (assimilated UKMO data for the UARS satellite) and instructions for accessing that data
- A comprehensive set of links to other WWW servers in the area of Global Change Atmosphere.
- An on-line form to enter your feedback

We are planning additions to the existing facilities to test the provision of access to restricted datasets through the Web, and we intend to set up a forum page to allow the free exchange of information about global change.

The most important part of the Experimental Demonstrator will be your feedback. Please try it out and tell us what you think of it.

The demonstrator is located at <http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/ceo/demonstrator.html> and will be active until 21 August 1995.

To obtain further information about the facilities of the BADC, contact:

Dr Peter Allan

British Atmospheric Data Centre

Space Science Department

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

Chilton, Didcot, Oxon OX11 0Qa

Tel: 01235 445123; Fax: 01235 445848; e-mail: badc@rl.ac.uk

IoP/EPG Meetings:**Urban Air Quality Meeting: Preliminary Announcement***Date and Venue: To Be Arranged*

Members may well be wondering what on earth has happened to this proposed meeting. Well, a few difficulties in the preliminary organisation have been sorted out and so we should soon see rapid progress. The general format of the meeting is still as that outlined in the last issue of the Newsletter. Those members that have already offered contributions should not be concerned. We will get back to you when we have more definite plans arranged.

To summarise the meeting content, four main headings are proposed:

- **The assessment of urban air quality** – Monitoring of all pollutants in the gaseous and particulate phase; sampling techniques and instrumentation; analytical aspects and emissions inventories.
- **Prediction of urban air quality** – Dispersion modelling; source apportionment (receptor) modelling; modelling developments (mathematical and statistical) and applications; physical and chemical processes in the boundary layer.
- **The Impact on environmental health** – Air pollution related illnesses; epidemiological studies; exposure estimates.
- **The Management and sustainability of urban air quality** – Policy issues; local and Government initiatives; evaluation of pollution control policies; integrated air quality management strategies.

The meeting will be composed of oral and poster presentations and it is hoped that the proceedings will be published either as a special issue of a journal or as a book. A call for abstracts will be announced in the very near future with the second call for papers following early in the new year. This is an important subject which affects us all and so we encourage all those with an interest to help us make this meeting a success.

Ranjeet Sokhi and Geoff Hassall

Environmental Physics Group Committee

Underwater Optics**19 October, 1995****Light in the Sea: Optical Sensors Underwater**

This is a collaborative venture organised by the Optical Group of the IoP and co-sponsored by the EPG and the Instrument Science and Technology Group of the IoP together with The Optical Sensors Collaborative Association and The Society of Underwater Technology.

This meeting represents the first time the Optical Group has concentrated attention of

the marine environment. Given the importance the role sea plays in the transport and exchange of energy around our world a full understanding of the underlying processes at work is essential. Turbidity and many other derivative optical measurements are important to oceanography, biological productivity and environmental and pollution assessments. The range of applications is already wide and is growing rapidly and so the general topic areas addressed in this meeting are Light, Active devices, and Sensors.

The meeting forms part of Photonex '95 at the Kettering Arena in Northamptonshire. Further information about the meeting can be obtained from:

Mike Wall, c/o Laurence Devereux,

Photonex '95

Mobilex Exhibitions Ltd.,

Sitex House, Station Road,

Addlestone KT15 2PR

Tel: (01932) 842852; Fax: (01932) 821663

IoP Annual Congress 1996**22–25 April, 1996**

The EPG will be holding a two-day meeting at next year's Physics Congress entitled **Physics and the Environment: processes and applications**. The exact dates for this meeting are not known yet.

Abstract: The solution to problems caused by increasing human activities and the rational use of limited natural resources depends on understanding the processes which transport materials and energy through the atmosphere, land and oceans. This meeting will explore these processes and will demonstrate how this knowledge can be applied by the environmental physicist to solve these problems.

Further information will be publicised later in the year.

EPG Visits:

A visit is planned to **Matra Marconi Space Systems** to see the ENVISAT-1 satellite in assembly and the full scale mock-up sometime in the Autumn. The visit will be limited to about 10 people.

Further details will be released later, or interested members can contact our Honorary Secretary, **Alastair McCartney** at the address given on the back-page of this newsletter.

Other Meetings:

British Association Annual Festival of Science:

Discovery and Invention

9-15 September, 1995

Venue: University of Newcastle

It is getting close to this years BA meeting in Newcastle. As usual the range of topics to be covered is bewildering but there really is something for everyone. The preliminary programme tells us that:

"The festival aims to encourage the discussion of the ethical, social and environmental issues surrounding science and to achieve greater public recognition of the contributions science and technology make to our lives."

This philosophy is reflected in the range of subjects covered and includes not only talks and discussions with leading edge scientific workers, but also hands-on programmes for families and young people, exhibitions showing the applications of science and technology in industry and the world at large, visits and field trips to local areas of interest, and debates on a broad range of ethical and social issues.

The details of the programme are too extensive to list here but more information and booking forms are readily obtainable from:

British Association for the Advancement of Science,

23 Savile Row, London W1X 2NB

Tel: 0171 973 3500 Fax: 0171 973 3051 **or**

British Association Festival of Science Office

University of Newcastle,

20 Windsor Terrace, Jesmond

Newcastle NE1 7RU

Tel: 0191 222 7470 Fax: 0191 281 4000

EPG members may find that joining the BAAS advantageous. For a very reasonable membership fee, members receive Science and Public Affairs magazine free of charge, plus a newsletter called SCAN which keeps BA members informed of all that's happening in science and technology. Membership information can be obtained from Maria Roy on (0171) 973 3064. The £20 membership charge ensures that both scientists and non-scientists alike can play a part in shaping Britain's scientific future.

Sensors and their Applications VII

10-13 September, 1995

Venue: Dublin

This Conference has been organised by The Instrument Science and Technology Group of the Institute and is to take place at University College Dublin. This is now a well established event and has been supported by industry, government laboratories and higher education establishments over its history.

Interest in sensor development has grown steadily over recent years, with an increasing acknowledgement of the important role that sensor systems will have to play in the technology-dependent world of the next century. The aim of this meeting is to provide participants with an overview of recent developments in the wide range of fields covered by sensors, as well as providing an in-depth coverage of the latest work.

For further information contact:

Sensors and their Applications VII

Meetings and Conferences

The Institute of Physics,

47 Belgrave Square,

London SW1X 8QX

Tel: (0171) 235 6111; Fax: (0171) 823 1051

World Environmental Congress

17-22 September, 1995

Venue: London, Ontario, Canada

"For the first time in history, the science, technology, and business of the environment are equally integrated into this most prestigious international environmental event."

This type of conference is an essential part of understanding how our world works and how we allow it to work given the constraints of industry, resources, etc. The occasional publicity coup illustrated by environmental pressure groups perhaps highlight problems, but the majority of change comes from within and from the continuous development of technology consistent with industries need for energy efficiency and within the very real constraints of limited investment resources. Bringing industry, policy makers and scientists into the same arena is an essential part of all our futures and it is to be hoped that this conference will succeed.

According to my information ... "World '95 will encompass a broad range of the timely environmental issues. The main themes of the Congress are as follows:

- Environmental Science and Technology Policy and Education
- University, Industry, Government Partnership for Technology Networking, Diffusion

and Transfer

- Innovative and Conventional Environmental Technologies for Pollution Prevention, Control and Remediation
- International Market, Business Opportunities and Investment
- Sustainable Development and Agenda 21

"World '95 is an International Conference and Trade Fair... Conference delegates will comprise of industry, academia, and government officials."

Included in this event will be the **Second International Conference on Advanced Oxidation technologies for Water and Air Treatment, AOTs-2**. This is a showcase for innovative technologies designed for the prevention or processing of pollutant materials in solids, liquids or gases. The first in this conference series was held in June last year and has since excited considerable interest in novel pollution control technologies such as those exploiting the chemical activity induced in the electrical breakdown of gases.

Further information about World '95 and AOTs-2 can be obtained from:

Dr. Hussain Al-Ekabi

*Chairman, World Environment Congress
Science and Technology Integration, Inc.,
The University of Western Ontario Research Park,
100 Collip Circle, Suite 110
London, Ontario N6G 4XB CANADA*

RSS '95: Remote Sensing in Action 11 - 25 September, 1995
The 21st Annual Conference and Exhibition of the Remote Sensing Society
Venue: University of Southampton

For further information contact the Society at:
Department of Geography
*The University, Nottingham NG7 2RD
Tel: (0115) 951 5435; Fax: (0115) 951 5249*

5th Annual European Environment Conference 11 - 12 September, 1995
Venue: University of Nottingham
For further information contact:
Elaine White at ERP Environment
Tel: (01274) 530408; Fax: (01274) 530409

Regional Groundwater Resource Modelling 29 November, 1995

Venue: Holiday Inn, Reading

For further information contact the Society at:

CIWEM Water Resources Panel

Lavinia Gittins

Tel: (0171) 831 3110; Fax: (0171) 405 4967

Oceanology International '96: 5 - 8 March, 1996

The Global Ocean - Exhibition and Conference

Venue: Brighton

For further information contact:

Spearhead Exhibitions Ltd.,

Ocean House,

50 Kingston Road, New Malden

Surrey KT3 3LZ

Tel: 0181 949 9222; Fax: 0181 949 8186

Implications of "Global Environmental Change" 1 - 3 April, 1996
for Crops in Europe: A Multidisciplinary Conference.

Venue: Churchill College, Cambridge

For further information contact:

Professor T H Thomas

Broom's Barn Experimental Station,

Higham, Bury St. Edmunds,

Suffolk IP28 6NP

Tel: 0284 810363; Fax: 0284 811191

The 20th United Kingdom Geophysical Assembly 10 - 12 April, 1996

Venue: University of Newcastle upon Tyne

This meeting is composed of *General Sessions, Thematic Sessions and Keynote Lectures.*

Further information can be obtained from:

UKGA20

Department of Physics,

University of Newcastle upon Tyne, Newcastle upon Tyne NE1 7RU

Tel: 0191 222 7333; Fax: 0191 222 7361

e-mail: UKGA20@ncl.ac.uk

WWW: <http://www.physics.ncl.ac.uk/ukga20/>

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Institute of Hydrology, Wallingford, Oxon OX10 8BB
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School of Environmental Sciences,
University of Greenwich

Anne Wheldon
Energy Group, Department of Engineering,
University of Reading

Alex Wilson
Ove Arup & Partners,
Research and Development

Edward Youngs
Silsoe College,
Cranfield Institute of Technology

Co-opted Members:

Richard Clarke
HM Inspectorate of Pollution,
Sheffield

† Newsletter Editors